

Analysis of Service Quality, Customer Relationship, and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty Cargo Air Industry: Mini Review

Bekti Setiadi

Sekolah Tinggi Penerbangan Aviassi, Jakarta

Corresponding Author: Bekti Setiadi; bekti_setiadi@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to look for gaps in previous research and to find the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. This study with the object of an air cargo company, this research uses a literature study that analyzes previous research. The findings of the previous article are a correlation between ontime delivery, service quality, customer satisfaction on customer loyalty. In this study, there are still many other variables that support creating customer satisfaction in air cargo companies

INTRODUCTION

The resilience of Indonesia's aviation industry in the face of the pandemic also depends on a number of factors. First, of course, no matter the circumstances, everyone needs goods to satisfy their needs. This may include food, clothing, shelter, and other necessities. Some of these goods must come from outside the region and require freight or air freight. Aviation is an attractive option due to Indonesia's archipelagic geographical location. Indeed, aviation has a number of advantages over other means of transport, such as speed, safety, and security as well as the ability to cope with different weather conditions. Regarding flight operations, the journey across Indonesia from the western tip to the eastern tip can be completed in one day. Of course, this is not possible with other modes of transport. Due to the essential need for air travel, the government does not ban it. In fact, the government encouraged this logistical operation to continue, even when people were banned from returning home. In line with the research (Koleoglu et al., 2018);(Susanto & Keke, 2020);(Achir et al., 2022).

The development of air or sea freight transport, also known as cargo, is currently showing an encouraging development. known as commodities, is currently showing an encouraging development. That is as evidenced by the growing number of freight companies around the world. Federal Express, TNT, UPS, and DHL a world-class freight companies. At the local level, JNT Express, Lion Parcel, TIKI, Wahana Logistics, JNE, ID Express, MSA Cargo, and Megacitra are the names of freight companies that have been involved in the field of freight transportation for a long time. people who have been working in this field for a long time. Not forgetting the airlines Airlines like Garuda, Lion Air, Singapore Airlines and others also have opened up the world of freight transportation. Currently, the aviation world is divided into two parts: Passenger flight (passenger aircraft), specifically an aircraft dedicated to Transporting passengers, luggage, goods (letters, documents), and special cargo flights (cargo aircraft), which is a type of aircraft that only transports goods. Starts with transporting goods, classifying types of imported goods, and procedures for receiving and releasing imported goods. Procedures for receiving and releasing imported goods. This approach is driven by three key actors: Sender (maritime operator), Consignee (consignee), and Carrier. The sender can be an individual or The unit operates directly without intermediaries or directly through freight forwarding agents. The manufacturer shipper sends the shipment to the forwarder/shipping agent and attaches it shipping documents. In line with the research (Anggorowati, 2018);(He et al., 2018);(Carbo & Graham, 2020);(Anthony & Benson, 2019).

Air cargo service is a type of cargo transportation by air. Air freight is often used by a number of businesses and individuals who want their goods to arrive quickly. Freight transport itself can be carried out by road, air, and sea, both within and outside the city. As we know, Cargo itself has a minimum weight for transportation, unlike parcel and document delivery services that have a low shipping weight. In general, the minimum weight for shipment is 5 kg. If sent by air, goods can arrive within a working time of about 2-3 days, unlike by sea and

land which can take up to 4-5 working days. Therefore, air cargo services are often chosen by communities and commercial players as a frequently used means of transporting services. In line with the research (Harahap, 2021); (Anthony & Benson, 2019); (Al Hazman & Achmadi, 2021); (Chao et al., 2023).

Competition in the air cargo business is positive, strictly speaking, because just like in sea and land transportation there is also competition. Thus, this can spur air transportation service providers to provide low prices and the best service so that it will be increasingly used by both shipping service businesses and the public. In the air cargo industry, cargo transportation service players are not dominated by two or three companies, so that healthy business competition can occur, either through providing low prices or better services. The increasingly fierce price competition with other transport companies has caused domestic transport companies to review their proposed pricing policies in order to create a perception of price fairness among customers. customers, thereby bringing satisfaction and loyalty to customers. Take into account not only price fairness but also customer perception of the company's image, which will also be related to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Price fairness and corporate image can then influence loyalty directly or indirectly through customer satisfaction. In line with the research (Jaya Sakti et al., 2021); (Hong & Nguyen, 2020); (Andrianto & Noor, 2013); (Wahyuhening et al., 2022); (Lustyana & Salsabila, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service Quality: For companies operating in the service sector, service quality is a very important factor. Because in marketing products and services, the interaction between producers and consumers takes place directly. The application of service quality as a characteristic of a product's form or function is one of the key elements of a company's strategy to achieve sustainable excellence. Either be the market leader or a strategy for continued growth. Quality is associated with customer satisfaction. Quality motivates customers to build strong relationships with the company. In the long run, businesses can increase customer satisfaction by maximizing satisfying customer experiences and minimizing unpleasant customer experiences. Every company must provide customer satisfaction with optimal offers and services, knowing that the company must be able to maintain its position in today's fierce business competition. In line with the research (Puteri et al., 2022), (Rossitya Dwi Setyawardani, 2021), (Andrianto & Noor, 2013), (Badariah et al., 2015), (Ningrum et al., 2021), (Somantri & Sukardi, 2019), (Riyani et al., 2021), (Mena-Giraldo et al., 2020).

Customer Relationship: Maintaining good relationships with customers is a company's obligation. Because customers are important assets of the company. Businesses will grow thanks to customers. So, it is very important for businesses, as entrepreneurs or business owners, to know about customer relationships. Customer relations is one of the company's strategies to maintain good relationships with customers with the aim of retaining existing customers and attracting them to make repeat purchases. A good relationship will help customers become loyal customers and not switch to other competitors. At the

same time, one way to facilitate communication with customers is to optimally manage customer data. The more customers you have, the greater your business will grow. This shows that consumer management in business is effective. In today's highly competitive business era, customer relationships are the key to achieving competitive advantage. Businesses that are able to build strong relationships with their customers tend to have an advantage in retaining existing customers and attracting new ones. In line with the research (Sahu, 2014), (Almohaimmed, 2019), (Lam et al., 2013), (Smaliukiene et al., 2020), (Shah et al., 2020), (Dimiyati & Subagio, 2018), (Brewer & Loren, 2021).

Customer Satisfaction: Customer satisfaction is an extremely important factor in the success of a business. Satisfied people tend to repurchase the product or service offered, recommend it to others and give positive feedback about the company. Therefore, it is important for businesses to understand this and develop effective strategies to meet customer needs and expectations. The main goal of customer satisfaction is to ensure that they are satisfied with their experience interacting with the company. By achieving satisfaction, businesses can achieve several important goals. In addition, it also contributes to improving customer loyalty. Satisfied people are more likely to remain loyal, make repeat purchases, and provide positive recommendations to others. Helps businesses maintain customer lifetime value. In line with the research (Asha et al., 2023), (Barik et al., 2023), (Camilleri & Filieri, 2023), (Nigatu et al., 2023), (Regolo, 2017)

METHODOLOGY

The research method used is a qualitative method based on the results of analyzing scientific articles from international journals whose research results are corroborated by researchers. Below is a data table describing scientific articles that provide results that support and prove this scientific article as follows:

Table 1 Distribution of articles, journals, and publishers

No	Authors & Title	Publisher	Journal	Result
1	(Ayodeji et al., 2023) Achieving sustainable customer loyalty in airports: The role of waiting time satisfaction and self-service technologies	Elsevier	Technology in Society	Significant
2	(Y. H. Chang & Chen, 2007) Relational benefits, switching barriers and loyalty: A study of airline customers in Taiwan	Elsevier	Journal of Air Transport Management	Significant

3	(Y. W. Chang & Chang, 2010) Does service recovery affect satisfaction and customer loyalty? An empirical study of airline services	Elsevier	Journal of Air Transport Management	Significant
4	(Prentice & Correia Loureiro, 2017) An asymmetrical approach to understanding configurations of customer loyalty in the airline industry	Elsevier	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Significant
5	(Chen et al., 2012) Customer perceptions of airline social responsibility and its effect on loyalty	Elsevier	Journal of Air Transport Management	Significant
6	(I. Agarwal & Gowda, 2020) The effect of airline service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in India	Elsevier	Materials Today: Proceedings	Significant
7	(Islam et al., 2021) - The impact of corporate social responsibility on customer loyalty: The mediating role of corporate reputation, customer satisfaction, and trust	Elsevier	Sustainable Production and Consumption	Significant
8	(Zhang et al., 2021) Informal interorganizational business relationships and customer loyalty: Comparing Guanxi, Yongo, and Wasta	Elsevier	International Business Review	Significant
9	(Matsuoka, 2022) - Effects of revenue management on perceived value,	Elsevier	Journal of Business Research	Significant

	customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty			
10	(Lee & Han, 2022) - Food delivery application quality in customer brand loyalty formation: Identifying its antecedent and outcomes	Elsevier	International Journal of Hospitality Management	Significant
11	(Balci, 2021) - Digitalization in container shipping: Do perception and satisfaction regarding digital products in a non-technology industry affect overall customer loyalty?	Elsevier	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	Significant
12	(Valderrama & Cameron, 2023) - Customer loyalty in two sided markets: Rider multihoming in the United States rideshare market	Elsevier	Research in Transportation Business and Management	Significant
13	(Chao et al., 2023) - Ascertaining the effects of service quality on customer loyalty in the context of ocean freight forwarders: An integration of structural equation modeling and network data envelopment analysis	Elsevier	Research in Transportation Business and Management	Significant
14	(Nusrat & Huang, 2023) - Feeling rewarded and entitled to be served : Understanding the influence of self-versus regular checkout on customer loyalty	Elsevier	Journal of Business Research	Significant
15	(R. Agarwal & Dhingra, 2023) - Factors	Cellpress	Heliyon	Significant

	influencing cloud service quality and their relationship with customer satisfaction and loyalty			
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RESULTS

Customer loyalty is a customer's commitment to consistently resubscribe or repurchase a product or service among many other options, and certain situations can influence behavior change. Several factors influence customer loyalty. Each element present must have a positive value in the eyes of the customer. Without achieving this value, it is difficult for customers to engage with the company, product, service or brand. A customer's commitment to consistently subscribe to or repurchase a product or service among many other options and certain situations can influence behavior change. A customer can be said to be loyal through repeat purchases, loyalty, and referrals.

DISCUSSION

Customer satisfaction is the part that deals with creating value for customers. Because creating customer satisfaction means bringing benefits to the company, specifically making the relationship between the company and customers harmonious, creating a good basis or creating satisfaction. customer satisfaction and form word-of-mouth recommendations that are beneficial to the company, so that customers are interested. arising when purchasing goods or using the company's services.

Customer loyalty is a deeply held commitment to repurchase or patronize a preferred product or service in the future, although situational influences and marketing efforts may influence this. converted customers. Consumer loyalty is the consumer's effort to maintain perceived loyalty, a feeling of quality, satisfaction, and intense pride in the product, followed by repeat purchases. Five ways to create and retain consumers: 1. Resolve customer rights, specifically customers' rights to be respected. When treating them according to their wishes and desires, to maintain their loyalty, the company must pay attention to their wishes and expectations regarding the performance of the company's products. 2. Stay close to customers, where this proximity is a valuable capital because the company will know the evolution of consumer desires, this proximity is very effective in quickly knowing expectations of consumers. 3. Measuring customer satisfaction is very important and must be conducted continuously, incrementally every 10 years to know consumer attitudes, especially their loyalty. 4. Create switching costs, including in the form of prices, as well as negotiated discounts where set prices can be reduced through negotiation with special attention to loyal customers . 5. Provide additional benefits, possibly in the form of gifts to customers. so they feel cared for and appreciated, which can ultimately bond them to stay loyal and faithful

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Today, the world of air cargo is facing some major challenges, such as the rapid growth of the reliable service/cargo company sector. As more and more airlines opened similar operations, these advances linked the world's countries to the global economy. In a globalized economy, businesses must respond to market trends while remaining responsible for protecting the environment. They also need to focus on customers if they want to succeed in the global market. The strategic management process helps organizations determine what they want to achieve and how they achieve valuable results. The importance of the strategic management role is more widely recognized today than ever before. Therefore, it is necessary to clearly define the strategies that companies must implement to welcome the era of globalization. The customer loyalty drive is a process or series of fundamental and comprehensive decision-making activities and the determination of how to achieve them, developed by management and implemented by all levels within the organization, to achieve the organization's sustainability goals.

FURTHER STUDY

This research can be used as a source of reference in the air cargo industry to increase service user loyalty and can be further developed with SEM AMOS software analysis tools and quantitative methods to get accurate results from respondents.

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